

INCREASING ACCESSIBILITY OF AUDIOVISUAL CONTENT USING WHISPER

Nina Rao and Simon O’Riordan - Emory University

Introduction

Captions are essential to the discoverability and accessibility of audiovisual materials. However, creating captions is often resource intensive. In 2023, we were awarded a grant to assess the viability of Whisper, an open-source automated speech recognition software, for captioning at Emory Libraries.

Method

We processed 250 hours of content through Whisper and Whisper.cpp. The resulting caption and transcript files were corrected by student editors using CADET editing software. We created a transcription style guide with resources and context for the collections. We collected data on processing time, power usage, editing time, and accuracy. We assessed accuracy using word error rate, first normalizing files and then comparing the Whisper and Whisper.cpp outputs with the editor-corrected versions.

Findings

Whisper was most accurate with content featuring minimal music, singing, background noise, or crosstalk. Its accuracy played a significant role in editing time, as did format; audio transcripts were faster to edit than video captions. Power usage (11W-60W per content hour) was comparable to other digital preservation activities in our department.

Whisper can be a viable tool for captioning and transcription due to its cost, accuracy, and ease of running locally for data privacy. However, human involvement is essential to identify and correct made-up text that occurs in the output. We also found that greater availability of captions led to increased demand for captioning work. Additionally, Whisper increased editors' work satisfaction; in performing the labor-intensive task of creating the initial text, it enabled them to focus on editorial decisions, which they found more engaging.

Conclusion

Access is fundamental to preservation; Whisper expands our capacity to provide captions and opens new opportunities for enhancing AV discoverability through using caption files in text searches and metadata enhancement - supporting digital preservation by ensuring that digital collections are available, useable, and understandable to users of all abilities.

Related literature

AI and Labor: Captioning Library Audiovisual Content with Whisper
<https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352241310534>

Increasing Accessibility of Audiovisual Content Using Whisper
<https://doi.org/10.48609/NA33-1Y19>

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Further information

nina.rao@emory.edu
soriordan@emory.edu